

Exploring Head Teachers' Leadership Training in Government Primary School of Dhaka City: Challenges and Possibilities for Implementation

Aklima Akter¹, Sarah Tabassum^{2*},

¹ Paikpara Government Primary School Ahamed Nagar, Paikpara, Mirpur-1, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh,

² BRAC University of Educational Development, Gulshan-1, Dhaka-1212, Bangladesh.

Accepted Jan 22, 2021

Published Jan 27, 2021

*Corresponding Author:

Sarah Tabassum

bornasiddik@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4526455>

Pages: 259-273

Funding: N/A

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):

Aklima Akter., Sarah Tabassum (2021). Exploring Head Teachers' Leadership Training in Government Primary School of Dhaka City: Challenges and Possibilities for Implementation. *North American Academic Research*, 4(1), 259-273. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4526455>

ABSTRACT

To improve upon a school to its desired manner, the head teacher needs to take the leadership role and gather a lot of knowledge and develop some skills. Relating it, this study was conducted in qualitative approach with the view to exploring the challenges and possibilities of implementing leadership training of head teachers of primary schools. Through conducting four interviews and one FGD data was collected, which showed that due to some challenges of training providers and the participant head teachers the training could not be implemented in proper way. The head teacher and the local education authority need to take the leadership role to implement the training knowledge and skills in the schools to improve the desired results.

1. Research approach

For my research topic I used qualitative research approach. The purpose of qualitative is to provide in depth understanding and natural setting. Patton (2002) defined qualitative research as attempting to understand the unique interactions in a particular situation. According to Pope and Mays (1995), qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings in an effort to discover the meanings seen by those who are being

researched (or subjects) rather than that of the researcher.

My topic is head teachers' leadership training in government primary school. I want to know what challenges and implementation in the school so I using this approach. It helped me to find out the answer of my research problem question. I think this approach is more suitable and explore together information. Head Teachers were the primary sampling unit. To understand the challenges and possibilities both good and bad side as well as success and failure of the training program were analyzed. Qualitative research approach had been chosen because it is in-depth and thick descriptive, can observe in a natural setting and context, focuses on process, understanding the meaning people have constructed and try to understand the perception.

1.1 Research site

In order to ensure the feasibility of the study, only GPS from Mirpur area of Dhaka city selected as study sample. My research area are eight government primary schools, Directorate of primary education office, one Thana education office and one Thana (training) resource centre. Selected schools, Thana education office and TRC are situated in Mirpur area of Dhaka city. I choose this institute for better data collection.

I am an assistant teacher of Government Primary school in Mirpur area. For this, I thought it was easy and suitable for me to collect data and go in-depth within this short time. My topic is to know head teachers leaderships' real scenario, its impact and challenges in government primary school. I have also seen the training authorities' point of view and challenges in leadership training. So I have selected TRC, TEO office and DPE.

1.2 Research participants

My research approach is qualitative. I used two types of data collection methods. There are four types of participants in my study.

For FGD method, I conducted FGD session with eight head teachers of government primary school. Among these eight head teachers, four teachers were old trained in head teachers leadership training in 2014-15 and four teachers was new tainted in 2017-18. I selected them for FGD to know their opinion about impact of leadership training.

I selected one DPE training related officer who was directly related to write the leadership training manual. I also have taken interview to TRC instructor and ATEO from TRC and TEO office who was trainer in head teachers' leadership training.

1.3 Sampling procedure

The population of the study was the primary head teachers of Mirpur region and the local education authority for monitoring and feedback for implementing quality primary education in primary sector in Mirpur region.

I selected the participant head teachers through purposive and convenient sampling for the FGD. I used purposive sampling to select the head teachers based on their training period. Four of the participant teachers were selected who received training in 2014-15 and four of them received training in 2017-18. The head teachers were selected in a convenient way based on their availability. I selected the ATEO's and TRC instructors for interview purposively both of the participant AETO are assigned in Mirpur region and Education officer DPE was selected based through purposive sampling who was involved in developing the leadership training manual for primary head teachers.

1.4 Data collection methods

In my study there were two types of data collection method. That's were interview and FGD.

In-depth Direct Interview:

I conducted interview with DPE training officer, TRC instructor and ATEO. I selected one DPE training related officer who was directly related to write the leadership training manual. I wanted to know to him about their vision about leadership training and present what is the real scenario. I also have taken interview to TRC instructor and ATEO from TRC and TEO office who was trainer in head teachers' leadership training. I thought they there was a scope to observed very closely head teachers performance on receiving this training. After receiving the training they also monitored and observed how the head teachers implemented the leadership training, that means what were the current practices and challenges to implement the leadership training. So my total interviewees were four people. In interview session, I conducted 1 hour per session.

FGD (Focused Group Discussion):

The main focus of the FGDs will be to find out teachers' opinion and perception. Human feelings, emotion, interest and its deepness can be measured by focus group discussion. This emotion, interest, feeling, belief cannot be measured by numbering. So, for this reason I have chosen focus group discussion of qualitative research.

To conducted FGD session there were eight head teachers and time allocated for 90 minutes. Among the 8 head teachers four teachers were old trained and four teachers were new trained. Every teacher's expression and experience were not similar so by FGD conversation i got different types and more data related my topic. These two types of head teachers have run their school their own ways and they have faced different challenges. By the conversation I have gotten their opinions about current practices, challenges and how they solve it to run way their school. These data was very helpful to understand the real scenario and worked over all with my research topic.

1.5 Role of the researcher

For conducting the study, I took appointment of the participant head teachers and ATEO and TRC

instructor. The data was collected through in depth interview and Focus group discussion (FGD) of the participant head teachers. I prepared the interview question based on the research question for the participant. I took the interview of the ATEO, TRC instructor and DPE official I also conducted the FGD of the participant head teachers to gather information and fulfil the purpose of my study.

1.6 Data analysis

The nature of my study is qualitative. After collecting data I transcribed it. I read the data several time and highlight it. After I categorized the data according to theme that directly related with research question. Then I reviewed the data and highlighted it. I analyzed the collected data from the interview and FGD through thematic analysis. At last I used special data for citation.

1.7 Ethical issues and concerns

Keeping ethical standard in research is not always easy. However, it is very much important. I will develop permission letter from my supervisor in the official pad of BRAC University. In this letter it will be stated that it is a voluntary participation and if there is still uncertainty, they are welcome to contact me and/or my supervisor at present or future. I will start my data collection process after the participant signed on consent paper and gave me formal permission. I will inform selected participants about the aims and objective of my research thus they can take informed decision whether they want to participate in the study or not. I will ask at least two times to every participant that do you want to withdraw you from the study. If you do so then you are fully free to withdraw yourself from the activities. No name (name of school and participant teachers" officers) will be used in report writing procedure. Mobile recorder was used at the time of FGDs with the permission of students. Anonymity will be followed not only at the time of thesis report writing, but also to the further verbal discussion.

1.8 Credibility and rigor

Firstly I have completed two research courses from BRAC Institute of Education development, BRAC University. For my research I selected one research topic according to my interest. After that I discuss with my faculties about this topic. After getting feedback and suggestion I select my topic and problem. Then I selected research question and sub questions after incorporating the feedback of my honorable faculties. After that I went to piloting. The pilot test was conducted to the validity and reliability of the objectives of checking whether or not the items involves in the instrument could enable to the gather knowledge. My colleagues and teachers helped to moderate or modify this data collection tools. After their feedback I prepared semi structure guide such as interview and FGD finally for data collection. I have developed data collection tools and these were modified by piloting and discussing with my faculties and peers. After that I presented my proposal in front of panel. After getting approval of my proposal I went to the field for final data collection.

1.9 Limitations of the study

This study has given me a scope to understand the existing status of different stakeholders' perspective towards leadership training for the primary school head teachers and possibilities and challenges to implement it in Mirpur area in Dhaka City. There are a few limitations of the study. Time constraints inhibited the data collection process to some extent. It would be much better to include views of parents, academic researchers, educationists and other stakeholders about the existing leadership perspective of government primary school. Limitation of time and Resources caused main problem in the study. Again some of the participant head teachers were not convinced to attend the interview.

2. Results

Head teachers' leadership training is for head teacher of government primary school. By this training head teachers achieve a lot of academic and administrative knowledge about rules and regulations, they know demand of the authority as well as develop some skill by practicing seven days in the school. As a result they know how to develop a school. That means this training is very necessary to the head teachers for whole school improvement. It is a great task to make the training but it is a great task to make the training manual for leadership training but the responsible persons not getting time to design it. The officers who are performing as a facilitator are always busy with their desk work and school visit. It is challenging for them to perform for the whole training. Most of the primary school has shorten of assistant teachers, there SMC is not properly functioned, and there political influence and other organization like PTA and SLIP committee try to get some economic benefits from the school, not to help the head teachers. As a result it is very much difficult for head teachers to improve the school properly by his training knowledge. They will be able to convince and motivate the assistant teacher, SMC, PTA and other stake holders to work in the favour of the school what will help to improve the school management system and quality of the school. This training will help the head teachers to improve a school as well as ensure quality primary education.

I found my data according to my research questions and categorized them two themes and sub-themes that flowed the data. The themes that were executed from the data were as follows:

- Perception of different stakeholders
- Effectiveness of head teachers' leadership training
- The findings of this study are presented according to the themes.

2.1 Perception of the different stakeholders

I found by the interview of different stakeholders few perception of the head teachers' leadership training. They said a trained head teacher done his work perfectly because he earns a lot of knowledge about

academic and administrative. A trained head teacher implements his acquired knowledge in academic supervision and administrative process.

According to the interview and FGD the assistant Thana education officer, TRC instructor, DPE education officer perception of head teachers leadership training is a head teacher needs to develop academic and administrative quality for whole school improvement for this reason this training is very necessary to the head teachers. They implement own school analysis own school activities to help the school management planning and implementation as a leader. After training they have gained much knowledge and experience about these. Now they are able to handle any situation. (Interview #2, Date: 11.10.2018, interview # 3, Date: 14.10.2018, Interview #4 Date: 15.10.2018, & FGD # 1. Date: 16.10.2018).

2.1.1 Perception of the different stakeholders are divided it into two sub themes

Development and use of the head teachers' leadership training manual. Skill/ knowledge acquired from the training

Development and use of the head teachers' leadership training manual.

For proper functioning of a school a head teacher have to be knowledgeable and skilful. From the head teachers' leadership training a head teacher can earn lot of knowledge about school management as well as develop some skill. The aim of the head teachers' leadership training is to improve the whole school management under the leadership of head teachers. In an interview of education officer in DPE, who write the head teachers' leadership training manual said:

To develop the quality of head teacher and also implementation such as academic supervision, to implement the curriculum, to implement the mentoring process, to analysis own school activities to help the school management planning and implementation as a leader. (Interview # 4, Date : 15.10.2018).

The training manual was developed to help the primary head teachers to meet their needs to conduct academic supervision, admiration, the help other assistant teachers and advising the other teachers to for improvement of their overall performance. The training manual was developed under the supervision of DPE and other stakeholders were related to for their expertise in the field of training. The Main purpose of the of the manual was to develop leadership qualities of the primary school head teachers and strengthen their ability to conduct supervision and provide necessary support for the teachers for the betterment of overall teaching learning process.

2.1.2 Skill/ knowledge acquired from the training

According to interview the assistant Thana education officers, TRC instructor and head teacher said that, after getting head teachers leadership training head teacher earn a lots of knowledge about academic, administrative, rules and regulation also they can know the demand of the authority as well as develop some skill by practicing seven days in the school and now they are able to handle any situation. (Interview #2,

Date: 11.10.18, FGD # 1, Date: 16.10.18).

An assistant Thana education officer added that,

There are many different between a trained and non-trained head teacher. Such as what is the meaning of light and dark? A non-trained head teachers' leadership training head teacher less informed about anything here a trained head teacher done his work perfectly and easily. (Interview #1, Date: 08.10.2018).

A head teacher needs to perform various types of work in school management such as academic supervision, fulfil the demand of authorities and to ensure quality education of the children. For this a head teacher need academic and administrative knowledge and skill. To earn this knowledge and to develop the skill head teachers' leadership training is must for every head teacher.

2.2. Effectiveness of head teachers' leadership training

Effectiveness of the head teachers' leadership training after getting the training the head teacher know that how to maintain records register and how to maintain the stake holders. They can improve the school environment and run the school properly.

I divided the themes into two sub themes of effectiveness of head teachers' leadership training:

- Challenges.
- Possibilities.

2.2.1 Challenges

DPE training related officer when they made this head teachers' leadership training manual they faced different types of challenges she said:

“We did not have any guide line, didn't get enough time, didn't get sufficient logistic support, there was given no responsibility to any specific person to monitor this work.” (Interview # 4, Date: 15.10.2018)

According to the FGD most of the head teachers said that, after getting the head teachers' leadership training when they implement their training knowledge at their own school they face different types of challenges such as to forming SMC, financial problem to buy sufficient teaching aids, bench ,table, and to implement SLIP activities.

In an interview assistant Thana education officer said:

“Head teachers' leadership training trained head teacher if come to know about any problem with the development of the school then we give feedback depends their problem. Firstly he said that this head teacher's leadership training enough for whole school improvement and the head teacher apply the leadership training knowledge and she monitor activities. Further she said that the head teacher face challenges to make PTA committee because he does not know how to make PTA committee even he does not know how to write regulation. So at a time he is saying two opposite thing.” (Interview #1, Date: 08.10.2018).

Another assistant Thana education officer said that, in the leadership training the schedule was very much

congested. In the training manual there were lots of topics to discuss elaborately and lots of work to do practically so it was challenging. As an assistant Thana education officer she has to stay very busy with various works so it is challenging to continue the training for 21 days continuously. Many of the head teachers were aged and their attitude was not so positive to learn so many things and practice in the school. (Interview # 2, Date: 11.10.2018)

Assistant Thana education officer (ATEO) state that, Some head teachers" complete their paper pencil are always okay but actually in the field level is not working. It"s the real scenario of our government primary school. Not work leadership in the field. Head teacher do not do their duty cordially. Because for example home visit, Suppose in a school there are four teachers including head teacher for supporting showing the higher authority only the right on the paper or fill-up the paper but maximum teacher not going to the student house. I visit the one student house two years ago in my Thana for finding the actual reason may one assistant teacher visited five class student house but when I went this student house this student mother said, no any teacher come in my house but the home visit from is fill-up so that gap and leadership is not working in the school or field. (Interview #1, Date: 08.10.2018).

2.2.2 Possibilities

Directorate of Primary Education training related officer think that there may be changed this manual in future because conception may be changed also mentality is being changed. On the basis of the manual keeping the similarity of future generation it has to develop but basic information will not change. By doing all his activities masterly he can acquire all qualities of appropriate leader. Head teacher will know how to maintain own responsibilities and he will help others how to maintain responsibility. By visiting advance school he can identify his own needs and shortness and takes proper steps. (Interview # 4 date: 16.10.2018)

Head teachers will show better performance in future with the help of this training. The head teacher will be more experts to build up their good relationship with different stakeholders. As a result it will be easy to ensure whole school improvement. ATEO said:

The teachers need to know various things about primary education, their duties and responsibilities, how a head teacher could practice various types of leadership in the school and various types of things to improve the school. This training will help the head teachers to improve a school as well as ensure quality primary education. (Interview # 2, Date: 11.10.2018)

In an interview TRC instructor said,

"The head teachers" leadership training in future will be easy to improve whole school management." (Interview #3, Date: 14.10.2018).

In an answer to my question, head teacher said about possibilities of head teacher"s leadership training, "By this head teachers leadership training a head teacher can transcend his leadership quality to assistant teachers and students. As a result leadership quality grows in them. In future all participants will be able to play a vital role to ensure whole school improvement." (FGD # 1, Date: 16.10. 2018)

There are lots of challenges in ensuring leadership training in primary school. The time for making model was not enough, writer has not enough training. Trainer was also busy in lot of activities, after lot of challenges. The training has some possibilities. This training make the head teachers some potentials. A head teacher could manage a school properly after this training and it will help in work school improvement. After the training the head teacher said the training programme helped them to plan and conduct their management related issues. Though the participant teachers have found some difficulties in the programme, they gained substantially. Most of the participant teachers said that the duration of the programme is not enough for them to learn the contents properly. Some of the participant teachers said that they face some problems to implement their learning in their school environment. Financial constrain and shortage of teachers and extensive workload of the both assistant and head teachers also causes problem for them to implement their learning in a proper way.

3. Discussion and conclusion

This chapter deals with summary of findings and discussion of these findings. The discussions were based on them major findings identified in chapter four:

3.1 Gap between training & implementation

The purpose of the study was to establish the relationship between leadership training of head teachers, training related officer and school performance in Government primary school. Though the leadership training has contributed to attain professional development of the primary school head teachers, there are some challenges and possibilities for improvement for implementing the leadership training in the working places. This section is divided into two major sections.

3.1.1 Training manual related

Result showed that perception of head teachers and local and central education authority head teachers“ leadership training is very important for leading a head teacher in a school. They believe that if a head teacher implements their achieving training knowledge proper way in their own school then a head teacher can be a skilled leader, the head teachers“ leadership training is clear that it is very essential for the head teachers for whole school improvement. So Leadership training is very necessary to the head teachers. Head teacher needs the leadership training to develop academic & administrative quality for whole school improvement. After getting the leadership training they are able to handle any situation. The leadership training for the teachers mainly focused on head teachers“ leadership manual activities and implementations on the school. The manual consists of the manual is a guideline for both trainees and trainers. The manual consists of instructions/support for the head teachers to conduct supervision and provide necessary support to the schools after the training. The leadership training for the teachers mainly focused on head teachers“ leadership manual activities and implementations on the school.

From the study it was found that after delivering the head teachers“ leadership training, there is no

obligation for the local education authority to follow up the progress of implementation in the school by the head teacher. So there is no scope of monitoring and mentoring. When implementing in school any head teacher faces any problem and contact with the local education authority, they try to give feedback.

Local education authority (ATEO, TEO, TRC instructors) regularly visit the school and follow up the overall activities of the school including implementation of leadership training, but they do not follow up the specific leadership manual related activities. A head teacher after getting the leadership training when he back his own school and implement the achieving training related knowledge they have no specific follow-up system. SO as a leader they cannot identify their learning gaps. After getting leadership training a head teacher change to a transformational leader but here they do not able to a transformational leader because their deficiencies remain.

3.1.3 Follow-up

By the training a head teacher earns a lot of academic and administrative rules and regulations of school management. School which makes a proper leader to fulfil the demand of authority and improve the school. According to the training manual after getting the training a head teacher will know how to maintain record register and how to deal with assistant teachers. Data revealed that due to some challenges in delivering the training and there is no follow-up specific system head teacher cannot perform training knowledge properly in the school. Such as assistant teachers are not making physical home visit rather then they make table visit. Similar result is found head teachers are failed to build leadership in the school to implement law and order in schools. To avoid unexpected situation with the local education authority during their inspection teachers make a table visit (false report). A very recent order from DD (inclusive education), DPE (Bangladesh) reflects the situation. It focused that home visit is taking place and there is no reality in it. He ordered the DPEO to check the home visit of about 5-7 schools by a skilled ATEO, (MOPME, 2018). Head teacher also fail to deal with SMC and there is happening a blame game between head teachers and SMC. Similar result is found the head teachers also failed to make proper communication with the community and failed to make partnership with SMC. Islam and Helal (2017) said, "Lack of SMC meeting is another problem in the row which is making hindrances on the way of its active role play. Most of the head teachers think that such meetings are of no use, while most of the SMC members reveal that HTs do not take step to hold SMC meeting,".

For that reason after arranging leadership training the local and central education authority who as performing as a leader do not proper follow-up. They do not find out the gap on the participants (Head teachers") in applying their training knowledge in their school and do not give them proper motivation and suggestion. According to Starling (2008) applying transformational leadership style to change the individual and social system in order to minimize the gaps between leader and followers. Leaders needs to understand the strength and weakness of the followers and try to give them motivation and suggestion. A head teacher for whole school improvement needs to proper supervision. If a head teacher wants to be a mentor or coach he has get the opportunity to practice. Therefore, after getting head teachers" leadership training they have

no proper follow up system so a head teacher do not implement their training knowledge. As a result his achieving knowledge remains limited.

Though a head teacher achieve many specific knowledge about whole school improvement through the head teachers' leadership training but there is no specific system to follow-up whether the head teacher implement or not their knowledge in the school. So a school does not get a proper leader.

3.1.4 Needs of leadership remain unmet

By this training head teachers achieve a lot of academic and administrative knowledge about rules and regulations. As a result they know how to develop a school.

3.1.5 Transparency

In this study according to the FGD most of the head teachers said that, after getting the head teachers' leadership training when they implement their training knowledge at their own school they face different types of challenges such as to forming SMC, financial problem to buy sufficient teaching aids, bench ,table, and to implement SLIP activities. On another data shows that, a trained head teacher if come to know about any problem with the development of the school then we give feedback depends their problem. Here, officers feedback the head teacher specific problem and give suggestion this problem but he/she didn't feedback or do not follow-up the leadership training related all activities. So the study revealed that the leadership training knowledge is not implementing in school level. Head teachers show lots of excuses. Some of the excuses are logical whether some are assume lame my long working experience. In this case local education authority and head teacher should apply resolute leadership style. (Fullan, 2010) authority should be strict about implementing. To improve the school they have to forget all the difficulties as well as they have to be motivation the teachers and have to give proper solution in their problem. They have to show them empathy also.

Fullan (2010) stated that collective capacity could be the big resource to face the challenge in implementing in the school. Though assistant Thana education officers or local authority is busy with their works. Head teacher can discuss with their other colleague about the problem. Different head teacher might be skilful in different matters. When some head teacher will meet to solve the problem they may find the solution easily.

3.1.6 Infrastructure & Serves more as an extended in-service training

There are millions of students in the primary education system. Therefore, when a country has large number of students they have need to a system or infrastructure. If these large populations are to be surrounded, some leadership roles are created for them and the leadership is professional developed. But there is no follow-up after professional development then there will be no value in this development. Therefore there are needs to specific infrastructure or format for the millions of primary students. If there have no any format or infrastructure then it will be not organized. But if it organized then there will be transparency. Especially the leadership has need to transparency.

Though a head teacher has to do different types of activities such as maintain school supervision, financial management, administrative work and so on so they have need to made a infrastructure or format. Because

head teacher get leadership training so they has need to follow-up system but here, after this leadership training there was no specific follow-up system. So this training basically somehow look like has been given for giving. One of the quotas is given for the filing. So their need to infrastructure or format so that the training can add value to the leadership training and it's also looks more often extended version of in service training. Every head teacher already done in service training after join their profession. After that they have gave the leadership training and after getting the training there is no follow-up system so that means leadership training more often refresher or an extended version of a in service training too. In fact generally leadership training has been given to strength the professional skills of the head teacher. Since it is not an in service training, so it's should be more importance this leadership training.

4. Conclusion

This qualitative research was set to explore the current practice challenges and implementation of leadership training. Challenges and possibilities for implementation of the government primary school in Dhaka city. By conducting interview and focus group discussion to the head teachers, assistant Thana education officers, TRC instructor and DPE training officer related to head teachers' leadership training in government primary school, data was collected.

From the finding of this study it was found that after getting the leadership training there was no specific monitoring or follow-up system. Teachers had less scope to practice in the school due to some challenge such as i.e. forming SMC, financial problem to buy sufficient teaching aids, bench, table etc.

This training has a big possibility. After performing resolute leadership by the head teachers and local education authority and applying collective capacity a school could be improved to its desired manner.

5. Recommendations of the study

This study finds that the teacher don't have proper understanding about leadership training and don't get enough time to discuss it in tight schedule. In some cases there is lacking in teachers pedagogical knowledge towards implementing their training in real-life situation. This study can guide the teachers to have concrete understanding about leadership role of in primary schools and conduct academic and administrative work. Monitoring should be strengthened from authority.

This study finds that most of the participant teachers face many problems to implement their leadership training. There is no monitoring for implementation of the training and the duration of the training is not enough therefore it may be increase for ensuring proper understandings and implementation of leadership training.

This study has been conducted in a small scale. Future research can be done in a large scale specially focusing on Mirpur area to find out the current practice of the leadership training and challenges and possibilities to implement it in a proper way.

Policy holder should be reform the head teachers' leadership training manual because of head teacher future

demand. So that they can applied their knowledge properly in their school as a good leader.

After getting training most of the time head teachers forget some training knowledge and when they implement their training knowledge they faces some challenges for these reason if the refresher training after every three years I think it will be very helpful to the head teachers..

References

Ali, S. M. (2011). Head teachers' perceptions and practices of school leadership in private secondary schools in Sirajganj district, Bangladesh.

Annual Primary School Census (2016), Monitoring & Evaluation Division, Directorate of Primary Education. Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, December 2016. Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.

Avolio, B. J., Waldman, D. A., & Yammarino, F. J. (1991). Leading in the 1990s: The four I's of transformational leadership. *Journal of European industrial training*, 15(4).

Bass, B. M. & Riggio, R. E. (2008). *Transformational Leadership*. Mahwah, New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc

Beatriz, P., Deborah, N., & Hunter, M. (2008). *Improving School Leadership, Volume 1 Policy and Practice: Policy and Practice (Vol. 1)*. OECD publishing.

Benson, K. (2011). *Assessment of Leadership Training of Head Teachers and Secondary School Performance in Mubende District, Uganda*. Online Submission.

Barling, J., Weber, T., & Kelloway, E. K. (2000). Effects of transformational leadership training on attitudinal and financial outcomes: A field experiment. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 827-832

Bandura, A. (2001). Social cognitive theory: An Agentic Perspective. *Annual Review of psychology*, 52, 1–26

Burns, J. M. (1978). *Leadership* New York. NY: Harper and Row Publishers.

Education policy, 2010. National Ministry of Education. Government of the people's Republic of Bangladesh

Fullan, M. (2010). The Big Ideas behind Whole System Reform. *Education Canada*, 50(3), n3.

Government of Bangladesh. (2010). *National Education policy 2010*. Dhaka: Ministry of Education, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.

Harris, A., & Muijis, D. (2005). *Improving schools through teacher leadership*. Maidenhead, Berkshire: Open University Press.

Hegstad, C. D., & Wentling, R. M. (2004). The development and maintenance of exemplary formal mentoring programs in Fortune 500 companies. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 15(4), 421-448.

Hart, C. (2018). *Doing a Literature Review: Releasing the Research Imagination*.

Sage.

Hopkins, D. (2001) *School Improvement for Real*. London: Routledge Falmer Hightower, A. M., Delgado, R. C., Lloyd, S. C., Wittenstein, R., Sellers, K., &

Swanson, C. B. (2011). *Improving student learning by supporting quality teaching*. Retrieved on, 3,

Islam, N.& Helal, A.(2017). *Primary School Government in Bangladesh: A Practical Overview of National Education policy-2010*. Canada International conference on Education (cice-2017) ISBN:978-1-908320-83-4

Kram, K. E., & Isabella, L. A. (1985). Mentoring alternatives: The role of peer relationships in career development. *Academy of management Journal*, 28(1), 110-132.

Kram, K. E., & Isabella, L. A. (1985). Mentoring alternatives: The role of peer relationships in career development. *Academy of management Journal*, 28(1), 110-132.

Kumar, C. R., & Shaktiprasad, S. *A Comparative Study on Rural-Urban Divide in Primary Education in Cuttack District of Odisha*.

Lydia, L. M., & Nasongo, J. W. (2009). Role of the head teacher in academic achievement in secondary schools in Vihiga District, Kenya. *Current Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(3), 84-92.

Lankau, M. J., & Scandura, T. A. (2002). An investigation of personal learning in mentoring relationships: Content, antecedents, and consequences. *Academy of Management Journal*, 45(4), 779-790.

Marzano, R. J., Waters, T., & McNulty, B. A. (2005). *School leadership that works: From research to results*. ASCD.

MOPME, (2015) *Third Primary Education, Dev.Pm (PEDP-3) revised*

Nath, S. R., & Chowdhury, A. M. R. (2000). *School without a head teacher: one- teacher primary schools in Bangladesh*. BRAC, Dhaka.

OECD. Centre for Educational Research and Innovation (CERI). (1998). *Staying ahead: in-service training and teacher professional development*. OECD, Paris, France.

OECD. Publishing, & Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development Staff. (2009). *Creating effective teaching and learning environments: First results from TALIS*. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development.

Pont, B., Nusche, D., & Moorman, H. (2008). *Education and training policy improving school leadership*. Vol. 1: Policy and practice.

Patton, M.Q. (2002). *Qualitative Research & Evaluation Methods*.CA:Sage

Pope, C., & Mays, N. (1995). Qualitative research: reaching the parts other methods cannot reach: an introduction to qualitative methods in health and health services research. *Bmj*, 311(6996), 42-45.

Richards, J., Austin, S., Harford, W., Hayes-Birchler, A., Javaherian, S., Omoluabi, O., & Tokushige, Y. (2008). *Improving the quality of education in Bangladesh*.

Shastri, R. K., Mishra, K. S., & Sinha, A. (2010). Charismatic leadership and organizational commitment: An Indian perspective. *African journal of business management*, 4(10), 1946-1953.

Schleicher, A. (2012). *Preparing Teachers and Developing School Leaders for the 21st Century: Lessons from around the World*. OECD Publishing. 2, rue Andre Pascal, F-75775 Paris Cedex 16, France.

Voon, M. L., Lo, M. C., Ngui, K. S., & Ayob, N. B. (2011). The influence of leadership styles on employees' job satisfaction in public sector organizations Malaysia. *International Journal of Business, Management and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 24-32.

Whitely, W., Dougherty, T. W., & Dreher, G. F. (1991). Relationship of career mentoring and socioeconomic origin to managers' and professionals' early career progress. *Academy of management journal*, 34(2), 331-350.

Wanjiru, M. R. C. *Influence Of Head Teachers' leadership Styles On Teachers' Job Satisfaction In Public Primary Schools In Kirinyaga West Sub County, Kenya*

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

